

Ultrasensitive measurement of both SARS-CoV-2 RNA and antibodies from saliva

Dmitry Ter-Ovanesyan (1)[‡], Tal Gilboa (1,2)[‡], Roey Lazarovits (1)[‡], Alexandra Rosenthal (3), Xu Yu (3,4), Jonathan Z. Li (3), George M. Church (1,5), David R. Walt* (1,2)

1 - Wyss Institute for Biologically Inspired Engineering, Harvard University, Boston, MA 02115

2 - Department of Pathology, Harvard Medical School, Brigham and Women's Hospital, Boston, MA 02115

3 – Infectious Disease Division, Harvard Medical School, Brigham and Women's Hospital, Boston, MA 02115

4 – Ragon Institute of MGH, MIT, and Harvard, Cambridge, MA 02139

5 - Department of Genetics, Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA 02115

KEYWORDS: SARS-CoV-2, Viral RNA, Antibodies, Saliva

ABSTRACT: Tests for COVID-19 generally measure SARS-CoV-2 viral RNA from nasal swabs or antibodies against the virus from blood. It has been shown, however, that both viral particles and antibodies against those particles are present in saliva, which is more accessible than both swabs and blood. We present methods for highly sensitive measurements of both viral RNA and antibodies from the same saliva sample. We developed an efficient saliva RNA extraction method and combined it with an ultrasensitive antibody test based on Single Molecule Array (Simoa) technology. We apply our test to the saliva of patients who presented to the hospital with COVID-19 symptoms, some of whom tested positive with a conventional RT-qPCR nasopharyngeal swab test. We demonstrate that combining viral RNA detection by RT-qPCR with antibody detection by Simoa identifies more patients as infected than either method alone. Our results demonstrate the utility of combining viral RNA and antibody testing from saliva, a single easily accessible biofluid.

TEXT:

Introduction:

The two main tests for SARS-CoV-2 infection are molecular tests to detect the presence of the virus (RNA or antigen) and serological tests to detect the presence of antibodies against the virus¹⁻⁷. Both tests have advantages and disadvantages. RT-qPCR, the main diagnostic test and current gold standard, is a sensitive method for measuring the presence of viral RNA, usually performed from nasopharyngeal (NP) or anterior nasal swabs¹⁻³. However, it has been shown that not all patients who are infected with SARS-CoV-2 test positive for viral RNA^{1,2,5,8-10}. There are several potential reasons for this: low viral load, variability in swabbing, or late swab collection relative to the time of infection^{2,5}. The time at which the swab is performed is important because, after initial infection, levels of virus sharply rise and then drop, providing a relatively narrow window at which viral RNA is present^{1,5,6,11-19}. Serology tests detect antibodies that develop against the virus during infection^{1,6}. These antibodies remain stable for at least several months, widening the time window of testing for SARS-CoV-2 infection²⁰⁻²².

Combining RNA detection with antibody testing has the potential to increase the sensitivity of RT-qPCR alone^{6,15,21,23-27} by reducing false negatives in RT-qPCR.

RT-qPCR tests for SARS-CoV-2 mostly analyze RNA from nasal swabs, while serology tests are generally performed using blood^{1,23,28-30}. However, studies have shown that both SARS-CoV-2 viral RNA^{15,31-34} and antibodies^{20,31,35} against the virus are present in saliva. Since saliva is easier to collect than either swabs or blood, its accessibility makes it an ideal biofluid for widespread diagnostic use. Research is still ongoing regarding how well saliva correlates to different types of swabs in terms of sensitivity of viral RNA detection^{31-33,36-38}. This will depend largely on several factors such as patient selection, sample collection, and RNA extraction methodology. Nonetheless, it is clear that SARS-CoV-2 viral RNA can be readily detected in saliva^{2,31-33}. Similarly, previous studies have shown a strong correlation between antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 in blood and saliva^{20,31,35}.

Although RT-qPCR is highly sensitive, there is great variability in the RNA extraction efficiency, which is generally performed using commercial kits. These kits have advantages in terms of ease, but are prone to supply chain limitations³⁹. Furthermore, using kits may lead to incompatibilities with upstream or downstream steps since the components are unknown to the user. Lastly, kits are not optimized for specific biofluids such as saliva, leading to potentially low RNA recovery. Antibody testing in saliva also presents challenges; namely, that concentrations of antibodies in saliva are much lower than they are in blood^{20,31,35} and that different isotypes may be present in the different fluids.

We set out to develop a highly sensitive test to detect both viral RNA and antibodies against the virus from the same saliva sample. We developed an optimized RNA extraction protocol that is highly efficient for saliva. We also adapted a Single Molecule Array⁴⁰ (Simoa)-based ultrasensitive test we previously developed for detecting SARS-CoV-2 antibodies in blood for use in saliva^{8,41}. Combining our RNA extraction protocol for RT-qPCR with this ultrasensitive antibody test, we are able to better classify COVID-19 patients as being actively or previously infected with SARS-CoV-2, demonstrating the utility of this approach for accurate diagnosis of COVID-19.

Results and Discussion:

In order to develop a highly sensitive test for both SARS-CoV-2 RNA and antibodies against the virus in saliva, we first optimized the RNA extraction. We developed two versions: a low-volume version (30 μ L saliva) that can be performed in a 96-well PCR plate and a high-volume version (300 μ L saliva) that can be performed in a deep-well plate. We started with a general method based on binding nucleic acids to carboxylated paramagnetic beads in the presence of a guanidinium thiocyanate lysis buffer^{42,43} (Figure 1a), and optimized each step of the protocol using saliva samples. To evaluate our extraction method, we spiked in known amounts of synthetic SARS-CoV-2 RNA or heat-inactivated SARS-CoV-2 viral particles into PBS or human saliva and then quantified recovery after RNA extraction by RT-qPCR. (Figure 1a, Supplementary Figure 1). We tested a large number of parameters using this approach until we arrived at a protocol that consistently resulted in 50-100% recovery in 30 μ L of saliva (Figure 1b,c). To maximize sensitivity, we opted to use more saliva (300 μ L) in a deep-well plate format. However, as it is difficult to elute into a small volume using a deep well plate, we included a transfer step in our protocol where we transfer the beads (during a 70% ethanol wash step) from a deep-well plate to a PCR plate, allowing us to elute the RNA in only 10 μ L (Figure 1a).

To see how our protocol compares to a commonly used commercial kit, we performed a head-to-head comparison with the ThermoFisher Scientific MagMAX Viral/Pathogen Nucleic Acid Isolation kit. We first extracted RNA from equal volumes of saliva spiked with viral particles and eluted the captured RNA into equal volumes (Figure 1d). In this comparison, we found that our custom protocol had more than twice the recovery of our custom protocol to MagMAX. We also compared our protocol to MagMAX using the maximum input volume and minimum elution volumes for both protocols using saliva with the same concentration of viral particles. In this case, our protocol recovered 16x more RNA (Figure 1e). We then compared our protocol to three recently developed protocols for measuring RNA from saliva

without purification. These protocols, SalivaDirect⁴⁴, TCEP inactivation⁴⁵, and 95 $^{\circ}$ C heating⁴⁶, all use a small volume of saliva (<10 μ L) since the final volume of RT-qPCR reactions is usually 20 μ L. We compared our high-volume RNA extraction to these three protocols using saliva containing the same concentration of viral particles. We found that we detected significantly more RNA in extraction-based protocols, largely due to the ability to use larger volumes of saliva (Figure 1e).

After validation of our RNA extraction protocol, we turned to combining RNA detection with antibody detection in clinical

Figure 1. Custom RNA extraction protocol recovers viral RNA with high efficiency. A) Schematic representation showing our bead-based extraction protocol in low-volume and high-volume versions. B) High-efficiency viral RNA recovery from PBS and saliva using custom protocol. PBS or saliva (30 μ L for low volume or 300 μ L for high volume) were spiked with 10,000 copies of synthetic SARS-CoV-2 RNA. Our custom RNA extraction protocol was performed, and extracted RNA was compared to input amount using RT-qPCR. C) Recovery of RNA is calculated as RNA level of extracted SARS-CoV-2 RNA relative to spike-in amount. D) Direct comparison of custom protocol with commercial kit using same input and elution volumes. RNA was extracted from 200 μ L of saliva with 50 particles/ μ L of heat-inactivated virus and eluted into 50 μ L using either our custom protocol or the MagMAX kit and quantified by RT-qPCR. E) Comparison of extraction and extraction-free methods. For all methods, saliva spiked with 50 viral particles/ μ L was used and the same volume of inactivated saliva or eluted RNA was compared by RT-qPCR. For comparison of RNA extraction methods, maximum input volumes (400 μ L for MagMAX vs. 300 μ L for custom) and minimal elution volumes (50 μ L for MagMAX vs. 10 μ L for custom) were used. Relative RNA Levels (log scale) represent each condition relative to spike-in aliquot on same RT-qPCR plate. Fold-differences relative to custom protocol are indicated above each condition. For the saliva control (no-inactivation), 8/12 replicates had no detectable levels of RNA and were not plotted. Four replicates were repeated across three different days for each condition (different colors represent different days). Error bars for all figures indicate Standard Deviation.

saliva samples from COVID-19 patients. We have previously developed Single Molecule Array (Simoa)-based ultrasensitive profiling of IgG, IgM, and IgA antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 nucleocapsid (N), spike (S), S1, and RBD protein targets in blood⁸. Our assay employs a bead-based, digital ELISA for high-throughput, automated ultrasensitive detection of antibodies in small volumes. Using only 40 μ L of saliva per sample (10 μ L for antibodies and 30 μ L for RNA), we characterized 12 antibody interactions and quantified SARS-CoV-2 RNA across 18 saliva samples. We tested two pre-pandemic saliva samples from healthy individuals, and 16 samples from symptomatic individuals who visited the MGH Respiratory Infection Clinic during the pandemic (see SI Table S1 for clinical characteristics summary). The patients were all tested by RT-qPCR from NP swab samples upon arrival to the clinic and saliva was collected on the same day.

Combined measurement of SARS-CoV-2 RNA and IgG, IgM and IgA levels against S1 (Figure 2, SI Figure S2) revealed that five patients were positive for either RNA, antibodies, or both, in saliva compared to three patients by NP RT-qPCR alone. Two patient samples were positive for antibodies in saliva but negative for SARS-CoV-2 RNA by RT-qPCR (in both NP swabs and saliva). Since these patients displayed severe respiratory illness upon presentation to the hospital, their RT-qPCR results were likely false negatives. RNA was detected in saliva for two of the three patients with positive NP swabs. For the patient with RNA detected in the NP swab but not saliva, antibody levels were above the threshold for IgA and IgM against S1. Since our previous work showed that IgA - S1 displayed the best separation between positives and controls, this sample would be classified as positive in our antibody assay. We also measured saliva from a subset of the patients at six late time points (>9 days after the first positive PCR). We found no RNA was detected but antibody levels were high for most of the immunoglobulin subtypes we measured, as expected (SI Figure S3). Finally, to see if we could achieve multiplexed detection of viral RNA and antibodies on the same platform from one sample, we developed a Simoa assay for the direct detection of SARS-CoV-2 RNA. Although we found this assay to be less sensitive than RT-qPCR, the Simoa assay detects RNA without amplification. We combined this assay with our antibody assay to detect RNA and antibodies spiked into saliva samples (SI Figure S4, Table S2), demonstrating multiplexed detection of RNA and antibodies on the Simoa platform.

Several studies have shown that saliva is suitable for both SARS-CoV-2 viral RNA detection and antibody measurements, but these measurements have not been made together using the same sample. In this study, we combined RT-qPCR with antibody measurements on a small number of symptomatic COVID-19 patient saliva samples. We demonstrate that combining these measurements identifies SARS-CoV-2 infection in patients that RT-qPCR alone misses, providing information that can help guide clinical decision making. This is particularly important in patients who present to the hospital with COVID-19 symptoms but have negative RT-qPCR results despite having been infected with SARS-CoV-2 (for example because the immune system has already cleared the virus).

To maximize sensitivity of RNA detection, we developed and optimized a high-efficiency saliva RNA extraction protocol without the use of kits. We found our protocol yields much

higher levels of RNA from saliva than a widely-used commercial isolation kit when performed manually. We also directly compared our RNA extraction method to several recently published no-extraction methods for SARS-CoV-2 detection by RT-qPCR in saliva. Although these methods greatly increase ease and throughput of RT-qPCR testing, this comes at a cost of sensitivity. Our high-volume RNA extraction protocol allows for a 30-fold concentration of the saliva sample in addition to the inactivation and removal of enzymatic inhibitors present in saliva. In a comparison utilizing saliva spiked with virus, our high-volume RNA extraction protocol led to the detection of at least 56 times more viral RNA than the use of inactivated saliva as input.

Figure 2. Detection of SARS-CoV-2 RNA and antibodies from the same saliva sample of hospitalized COVID-19 patients on initial day of hospitalization. RT-qPCR Ct levels (red rectangular) and Simoa antibody mean AEB (average enzyme per bead) levels (gray triangles) for IgG, IgM, and IgA against S1 subunit. The samples were divided into three groups: pre-pandemic control samples (left, n=2), saliva samples from patients who tested negative by RT-qPCR from nasopharyngeal swabs (NP-PCR negative, middle, n=7) and saliva samples from patients who tested positive by RT-qPCR from nasopharyngeal swabs (NP-PCR positive, right, n=3). Conditions for RT-qPCR where signal is undetected are set to Ct = 40. All antibody samples were measured with two technical replicates. Black dotted lines indicate antibody threshold levels, defined as three standard deviations above the highest pre-pandemic controls signals. Samples on or below the dotted line are considered negative.

To maximize the sensitivity of our antibody measurements, we employed assays that we recently developed using Single Molecule Array (Simoa) technology⁸. The high sensitivity of these assays is particularly advantageous in saliva, where antibody levels are known to be low^{20,31,35}. We have also demon-

strated that antibody measurements can be combined with direct, amplification-free detection of RNA in saliva samples, which expands on previous work applying the Simoa platform for multi-analyte detection^{47–49}. We envision that the sensitivity of the RNA assay can be further improved, for example, by adding Cas13a-based detection⁵⁰. Future studies may also incorporate additional protein biomarkers in saliva to measure inflammation (cytokines, etc.) or other aspects of host response to increase the utility of multiplexed saliva diagnostics for COVID-19.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supplementary Information (PDF) includes detailed experimental methods, Supplementary Figures 1–4, and Supplementary Tables 1–2

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

* Corresponding author, email: dwalt@bwh.harvard.edu

‡These authors contributed equally.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledge funding from the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation for this work. The MGH/MassCPR COVID-19 biorepository was supported by a gift from Ms. Enid Schwartz, by the Mark and Lisa Schwartz Foundation, the Massachusetts Consortium for Pathogen Readiness and the Ragon Institute of MGH, MIT and Harvard.

COMPETING INTERESTS:

DRW has a financial interest in Quanterix Corporation, a company that develops an ultra-sensitive digital immunoassay platform. He is an inventor of the Simoa technology, a founder of the company and also serves on its Board of Directors. His interests were reviewed and are managed by BWH and Partners HealthCare in accordance with their conflict of interest policies. GMC commercial interests: <http://arep.med.harvard.edu/gmc/tech.html>

REFERENCES

- Ravi N, Cortade DL, Ng E, Wang SX. Diagnostics for SARS-CoV-2 detection: A comprehensive review of the FDA-EUA COVID-19 testing landscape. *Biosens Bioelectron.* 2020;165:112454. doi:10.1016/j.bios.2020.112454
- Feng W, Newbigging AM, Le C, et al. Molecular Diagnosis of COVID-19: Challenges and Research Needs. *Anal Chem.* 2020;92(15):10196–10209. doi:10.1021/acs.analchem.0c02060
- Venter M, Richter K. Towards effective diagnostic assays for COVID-19: a review. *J Clin Pathol.* 2020;73(7):370–377. doi:10.1136/jclinpath-2020-206685
- Tang Y-W, Schmitz JE, Persing DH, Stratton CW. Laboratory Diagnosis of COVID-19: Current Issues and Challenges. *J Clin Microbiol.* 2020;58(6). doi:10.1128/JCM.00512-20
- Wiersinga WJ, Rhodes A, Cheng AC, Peacock SJ, Prescott HC. Pathophysiology, Transmission, Diagnosis, and Treatment of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19): A Review. *JAMA.* 2020;324(8):782–793. doi:10.1001/jama.2020.12839
- Sethuraman N, Jeremiah SS, Ryo A. Interpreting Diagnostic Tests for SARS-CoV-2. *JAMA.* 2020;323(22):2249–2251. doi:10.1001/jama.2020.8259
- Udugama B, Kadhiresan P, Kozlowski HN, et al. Diagnosing COVID-19: The Disease and Tools for Detection. *ACS Nano.* 2020;14(4):3822–3835. doi:10.1021/acsnano.0c02624
- Norman M, Gilboa T, Ogata AF, et al. Ultrasensitive high-resolution profiling of early seroconversion in patients with COVID-19. *Nat Biomed Eng.* Published online 2020. doi:10.1038/s41551-020-00611-x
- Li Y, Xia L. Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19): Role of Chest CT in Diagnosis and Management. *AJR Am J Roentgenol.* 2020;214(6):1280–1286. doi:10.2214/AJR.20.22954
- Wang Y, Kang H, Liu X, Tong Z. Combination of RT-qPCR testing and clinical features for diagnosis of COVID-19 facilitates management of SARS-CoV-2 outbreak. *J Med Virol.* 2020;92(6):538–539. doi:10.1002/jmv.25721
- Arons MM, Hatfield KM, Reddy SC, et al. Presymptomatic SARS-CoV-2 Infections and Transmission in a Skilled Nursing Facility. *N Engl J Med.* 2020;382(22):2081–2090. doi:10.1056/NEJMoa2008457
- Bi Q, Wu Y, Mei S, et al. Epidemiology and transmission of COVID-19 in 391 cases and 1286 of their close contacts in Shenzhen, China: a retrospective cohort study. *Lancet Infect Dis.* 2020;20(8):911–919. doi:10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30287-5
- Savvides C, Siegel R. Asymptomatic and presymptomatic transmission of SARS-CoV-2: A systematic review. *medRxiv Prepr Serv Heal Sci.* Published online June 17, 2020:2020.06.11.20129072. doi:10.1101/2020.06.11.20129072
- He X, Lau EHY, Wu P, et al. Temporal dynamics in viral shedding and transmissibility of COVID-19. *Nat Med.* 2020;26(5):672–675. doi:10.1038/s41591-020-0869-5
- To KK-W, Tsang OT-Y, Leung W-S, et al. Temporal profiles of viral load in posterior oropharyngeal saliva samples and serum antibody responses during infection by SARS-CoV-2: an observational cohort study. *Lancet Infect Dis.* 2020;20(5):565–574. doi:10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30196-1
- Zou L, Ruan F, Huang M, et al. SARS-CoV-2 Viral Load in Upper Respiratory Specimens of Infected Patients. *N Engl J Med.* 2020;382(12):1177–1179. doi:10.1056/NEJMc2001737
- Wölfel R, Corman VM, Guggemos W, et al. Virological assessment of hospitalized patients with COVID-2019. *Nature.* 2020;581(7809):465–469. doi:10.1038/s41586-020-2196-x
- Yongchen Z, Shen H, Wang X, et al. Different longitudinal patterns of nucleic acid and serology testing results based on disease severity of COVID-19 patients. *Emerg Microbes Infect.* 2020;9(1):833–836. doi:10.1080/22221751.2020.1756699
- Lauer SA, Grantz KH, Bi Q, et al. The Incubation Period of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) From Publicly Reported Confirmed Cases: Estimation and Application. *Ann Intern Med.* 2020;172(9):577–582. doi:10.7326/M20-0504
- Isho B, Abe KT, Zuo M, et al. Persistence of serum and saliva antibody responses to SARS-CoV-2 spike antigens in COVID-19 patients. *Sci Immunol.* 2020;5(52).
- Wajnberg A, Amanat F, Firpo A, et al. Robust neutralizing antibodies to SARS-CoV-2 infection persist for months. *Science (80-).* Published online October 28,

- 2020:eabd7728. doi:10.1126/science.abd7728
22. Iyer AS, Jones FK, Nodoushani A, et al. Persistence and decay of human antibody responses to the receptor binding domain of SARS-CoV-2 spike protein in COVID-19 patients. *Sci Immunol*. 2020;5(52):eabe0367. doi:10.1126/sciimmunol.abe0367
23. Rongqing Z, Li M, Song H, et al. Early Detection of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 Antibodies as a Serologic Marker of Infection in Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019. *Clin Infect Dis an Off Publ Infect Dis Soc Am*. 2020;71(16):2066-2072. doi:10.1093/cid/ciaa523
24. Lee Y-L, Liao C-H, Liu P-Y, et al. Dynamics of anti-SARS-Cov-2 IgM and IgG antibodies among COVID-19 patients. *J Infect*. 2020;81(2):e55-e58. doi:10.1016/j.jinf.2020.04.019
25. Guo L, Ren L, Yang S, et al. Profiling Early Humoral Response to Diagnose Novel Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19). *Clin Infect Dis*. 2020;71(15):778-785. doi:10.1093/cid/ciaa310
26. Zhao J, Yuan Q, Wang H, et al. Antibody Responses to SARS-CoV-2 in Patients With Novel Coronavirus Disease 2019. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2020;71(16):2027-2034. doi:10.1093/cid/ciaa344
27. Long Q-X, Liu B-Z, Deng H-J, et al. Antibody responses to SARS-CoV-2 in patients with COVID-19. *Nat Med*. 2020;26(6):845-848. doi:10.1038/s41591-020-0897-1
28. Amanat F, Stadlbauer D, Strohmaier S, et al. A serological assay to detect SARS-CoV-2 seroconversion in humans. *Nat Med*. 2020;26(7):1033—1036. doi:10.1038/s41591-020-0913-5
29. Padoan A, Sciacovelli L, Basso D, et al. IgA-Ab response to spike glycoprotein of SARS-CoV-2 in patients with COVID-19: A longitudinal study. *Clin Chim Acta*. 2020;507:164-166. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cca.2020.04.026
30. Padoan A, Cosma C, Sciacovelli L, Faggian D, Plebani M. Analytical performances of a chemiluminescence immunoassay for SARS-CoV-2 IgM/IgG and antibody kinetics. *Clin Chem Lab Med*. 2020;58(7):1081-1088. doi:10.1515/cclm-2020-0443
31. Ceron JJ, Lamy E, Martinez-Subiela S, et al. Use of Saliva for Diagnosis and Monitoring the SARS-CoV-2: A General Perspective. *J Clin Med*. 2020;9(5):1491. doi:10.3390/jcm9051491
32. To KK-W, Tsang OT-Y, Yip CC-Y, et al. Consistent Detection of 2019 Novel Coronavirus in Saliva. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2020;71(15):841-843. doi:10.1093/cid/ciaa149
33. Wyllie AL, Fournier J, Casanovas-Massana A, et al. Saliva or Nasopharyngeal Swab Specimens for Detection of SARS-CoV-2. *N Engl J Med*. 2020;383(13):1283-1286. doi:10.1056/NEJMc2016359
34. Williams E, Bond K, Zhang B, Putland M, Williamson DA. Saliva as a Noninvasive Specimen for Detection of SARS-CoV-2. *J Clin Microbiol*. 2020;58(8):e00776-20. doi:10.1128/JCM.00776-20
35. Randad PR, Pisanic N, Kruczynski K, et al. COVID-19 serology at population scale: SARS-CoV-2-specific antibody responses in saliva. *J Clin Microbiol*. Published online October 2020:02204-02220. doi:10.1128/JCM.02204-20
36. Medeiros da Silva RC, Nogueira Marinho LC, Neto de Araújo Silva D, Costa de Lima K, Pirihi FQ, Luz de Aquino Martins AR. Saliva as a possible tool for the SARS-CoV-2 detection: a review. *Travel Med Infect Dis*. Published online November 18, 2020:101920. doi:10.1016/j.tmaid.2020.101920
37. Sui Z, Zhang Y, Tu S, et al. Evaluation of saliva as an alternative diagnostic specimen source for SARS-CoV-2 detection by RT-dPCR. *J Infect*. Published online November 26, 2020:S0163-4453(20)30716-7. doi:10.1016/j.jinf.2020.11.023
38. Sakanashi D, Asai N, Nakamura A, et al. Comparative evaluation of nasopharyngeal swab and saliva specimens for the molecular detection of SARS-CoV-2 RNA in Japanese patients with COVID-19. *J Infect Chemother Off J Japan Soc Chemother*. 2021;27(1):126-129. doi:10.1016/j.jiac.2020.09.027
39. Tromberg BJ, Schwetz TA, Pérez-Stable EJ, et al. Rapid Scaling Up of Covid-19 Diagnostic Testing in the United States - The NIH RADx Initiative. *N Engl J Med*. 2020;383(11):1071-1077. doi:10.1056/NEJMr2022263
40. Rissin DM, Kan CW, Campbell TG, et al. Single-molecule enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay detects serum proteins at subfemtomolar concentrations. *Nat Biotechnol*. 2010;28(6):595-599. doi:10.1038/nbt.1641
41. Ogata AF, Maley AM, Wu C, et al. Ultra-sensitive Serial Profiling of SARS-CoV-2 Antigens and Antibodies in Plasma to Understand Disease Progression in COVID-19 Patients with Severe Disease. *Clin Chem*. Published online September 2020. doi:10.1093/clinchem/hvaa213
42. Boom R, Sol CJ, Salimans MM, Jansen CL, Wertheim-van Dillen PM, van der Noordaa J. Rapid and simple method for purification of nucleic acids. *J Clin Microbiol*. 1990;28(3):495-503. doi:10.1128/JCM.28.3.495-503.1990
43. Oberacker P, Stepper P, Bond DM, et al. Bio-On-Magnetic-Beads (BOMB): Open platform for high-throughput nucleic acid extraction and manipulation. *PLoS Biol*. 2019;17(1):e3000107. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000107
44. Vogels CBF, Watkins AE, Harden CA, et al. SalivaDirect: A simplified and flexible platform to enhance SARS-CoV-2 testing capacity. *medRxiv*. Published online January 1, 2020:2020.08.03.20167791. doi:10.1101/2020.08.03.20167791
45. Rabe BA, Cepko C. SARS-CoV-2 detection using isothermal amplification and a rapid, inexpensive protocol for sample inactivation and purification. *Proc Natl Acad Sci*. 2020;117(39):24450 LP - 24458. doi:10.1073/pnas.2011221117
46. Smyrlaki I, Ekman M, Lentini A, et al. Massive and rapid COVID-19 testing is feasible by extraction-free SARS-CoV-2 RT-PCR. *Nat Commun*. 2020;11(1):4812. doi:10.1038/s41467-020-18611-5
47. Gilboa T, Maley AM, Ogata AF, Wu C, Walt DR. Sequential Protein Capture in Multiplex Single Molecule Arrays: A Strategy for Eliminating Assay Cross-Reactivity. *Adv Healthc Mater*. 2020;n/a(n/a):2001111. doi:https://doi.org/10.1002/adhm.202001111
48. Wang X, Walt DR. Simultaneous detection of small molecules, proteins and microRNAs using single molecule arrays. *Chem Sci*. 2020;11(30):7896-7903. doi:10.1039/D0SC02552F
49. Cohen L, Hartman MR, Amardey-Wellington A, Walt DR. Digital direct detection of microRNAs using single molecule arrays. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2017;45(14):e137-e137. doi:10.1093/nar/gkx542
50. Fozouni P, Son S, Díaz de León Derby M, et al. Amplification-free detection of SARS-CoV-2 with CRISPR-Cas13a and mobile phone microscopy. *Cell*. Published online December 4, 2020. doi:10.1016/j.cell.2020.12.001

Table of Contents (TOC) graphic:

